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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITY LINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождидинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev	
Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov	
S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich	
Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA:	

AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Xazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
THE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliyo Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadilloevna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibodulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Сайтмуратов Сайтмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT.....	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	

FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF TRANSFORMATION	391
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	395
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	399
Бутаева Сабина Холиёровна	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND CAPITAL OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES	404
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)	416
Shodiev Akmal O'ktamjon ugli	
IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT	422
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT FOR DIGITAL TRACKING OF FOOD EXPORTIMPORT FLOWS.....	426
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	

THE PAYBACK PERIOD METHOD IN PERSONAL FINANCE: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	438
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTIVE FIBONACCI STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODEL FOR GOLD TRADING: EVIDENCE FROM THE XAU/USD MARKET	447
Tukmirzaev Kamol Mumin ugli	
DEVELOPING MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL TRADE THROUGH A BRAND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: DIRECTIONS AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES.....	455
Shohboz Ro‘zimatov Hamdambek o‘g‘li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	461
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	466
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ НА РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	472
Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN’S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA’S DIGITAL ECONOMY	481
Zhang Zhe	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ	487
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KASHKADARYA REGION	493
Azimov Islom	
ASSESSING DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	498
Berdiyev Temurbek Makhmudullo ugli	
РАЗРАБОТКА ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ (CGI) ДЛЯ БАНКОВ С ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ.....	506
Жумадуллаева Дурдона Шухрат кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY-BASED GOVERNANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: LEVERAGING AI AND DATA FOR IMPROVED INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE	512
Olimjonov Abbosjon Olimjonovich	
THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT ON NATIONAL ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE ESSENCE, TASKS, AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES OF INTERNAL AUDIT IN LEASING TRANSACTIONS.....	536
Sadritdinov Bakhodir Bakhtiyarovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN THE MINING SECTOR.....	543
Oybekova S.K.	
METHODOLOGY FOR REFLECTING GOODWILL, INTANGIBLE ASSETS, AND INVESTMENTS IN CONSOLIDATION.....	548
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY:	

CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	554
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
THE DMED INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A FOUNDATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL E-HEALTH SYSTEM	561
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN GLOBAL MARKETS	566
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF NURSERY FARMS	573
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM MARKET AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PLATFORM ECONOMY.....	580
Jumayev Bobomurod Nurmaxmat o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ «ЖЕНСКОГО» ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	586
Холбаева Сабина Рустамовна	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЁТОМ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В МАЛОМ И СРЕДНЕМ БИЗНЕСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	595
Камбарова Шахнозахон Мирвахитовна	
ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	603
Umaraliyev Sarvar Rustamovich	
TERRITORIAL DISPROPORTIONS IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURIST FLOWS.....	610
A.Sh. Daliev	
T.Sh. Muxiddinov	
METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP MECHANISMS.....	616
Mirumar Abdulla Ugli Usmonov	
IMPROVEMENT OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN THE FISHERY INDUSTRY: PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE ADAPTATION OF IFRS, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG REPORTING FOR FISHERY CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	620
Shodiev Aslam Rakhmatilloevich	
Alikulov Abdumumin Ismatovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP FRUIT PROCESSING ENTERPRISES BASED ON THE CLUSTER SYSTEM	627
Yusufova Laylo G'ayrat qizi	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN BANKING SERVICE DEVELOPMENT	635
Mamutova Ayygul Kalmurzaevna	
IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED AUDIT TECHNIQUES (CAATS) AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES IN THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.....	642
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND THE FORMATION OF KEY AUDIT MATTERS (ISA 701)	649
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	656
Abdullayev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SERICULTURE DEVELOPMENT: ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS APPLICABLE TO UZBEKISTAN.....	664
Janikulova Lobar Shakarbaevna	
SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE THROUGH ESG AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT: A GREEN MARKETING PERSPECTIVE	670
Khaydarova Kamola Axinjanovna	
SYSTEM AND STRATEGY FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN AN ORGANIZATION	675
Azimov Tolmas Nematullayevich	
MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF SMALL BUSINESSES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	682
Abdusalim Shavkatov	
STRUCTURE AND DYNAMICS OF BANK LOANS	689
Jorayeva Zarifa	
THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MODERN APPROACHES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF BUSINESS PROCESSES OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	698
Djumaniyazova Mo‘tabarkhan Ravshanbekovna	
IMPROVING THE METHOD OF ASSESSING MARKETING ACTIVITY EFFICIENCY IN SEWING AND KNITTING ENTERPRISES	704
Muminov Dilmurod Tokhtasinovich	
MODERN INDICATORS FOR EVALUATING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNATIONAL GRANTS AND TARGETED PROGRAMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	713
Ulugbek Qudrat ugli Almardanov	
STAGES OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES’ TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY UNDER MANAGEMENT TRANSFORMATION.....	717
Matluba Nematovna Abdullayeva	
Kamoliddin Fakhridin ugli Nuriddinov	
THE ROLE OF INFLATION TARGETING AND INTEREST RATE POLICY IN MANAGING CAPITAL FLOWS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN AND EMERGING ECONOMIES.....	722
Mamadjanov Farrux	
IMPROVING THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN CORPORATE ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT.....	731
Kuchkarov Ulugbek Taxirovich	
ISSUES OF FORMING AND EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING INVESTMENT RESOURCES IN FUEL AND ENERGY ENTERPRISES.....	735
Shukurillaev Jahongir Botir o‘g‘li	

ISSUES OF FORMING AND EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING INVESTMENT RESOURCES IN FUEL AND ENERGY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article examines the formation and efficient utilization of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises. The study analyzes the importance of investment in the energy sector at both the global and national levels, examines the main sources of financing, and substantiates the need to diversify investment mechanisms. Drawing on international experience and the specific conditions of Uzbekistan, the study develops practical recommendations aimed at improving investment efficiency, reducing capital costs, and strengthening energy security.

Keywords: fuel and energy enterprises, investment resources, investment activity, financing sources, energy security, energy infrastructure, cost of capital, WACC, NPV, IRR, green finance, public-private partnership, international financial institutions, investment efficiency, risk management, digital monitoring, Uzbekistan's energy sector.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы формирования и эффективного использования инвестиционных ресурсов на предприятиях топливно-энергетического комплекса. Исследование раскрывает значение инвестиционной деятельности в энергетическом секторе на глобальном и национальном уровнях, анализирует основные источники финансирования и обосновывает необходимость диверсификации инвестиционных механизмов. На основе международного опыта и с учетом специфики Республики Узбекистан разработаны практические рекомендации, направленные на повышение эффективности инвестиционной деятельности, снижение стоимости капитала и укрепление энергетической безопасности.

Ключевые слова: предприятия топливно-энергетического комплекса, инвестиционные ресурсы, инвестиционная деятельность, источники финансирования, энергетическая безопасность, энергетическая инфраструктура, стоимость капитала, WACC, NPV, IRR, зеленое финансирование, государственно-частное партнерство, международные финансовые институты, эффективность инвестиций, управление рисками, цифровой мониторинг, энергетический сектор Узбекистана.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical and methodological aspects of investment activity, capital structure, financing sources, and investment efficiency have been extensively examined in the economic literature. J. M. Keynes emphasized the fundamental role of investment in stimulating aggregate demand and promoting sustainable economic growth. According to Keynesian theory, investment serves as one of the principal drivers of economic development, employment creation, and the expansion of productive capacity.

F. Modigliani and M. Miller developed the theory of capital structure, examining the relationship between debt financing, equity financing, and enterprise value. Their framework provides an important basis for determining the optimal balance between borrowed and own capital in investment financing. In the context of fuel and energy enterprises, this theory contributes to understanding how capital structure influences the cost of capital and the financial sustainability of enterprises.

H. Markowitz's portfolio theory also provides an important theoretical foundation for the formation of investment resources. According to this theory, diversification of both investment projects and financing sources contributes to reducing investment risk while enhancing overall investment efficiency. For fuel and energy enterprises, diversification should therefore be applied not only to investment portfolios but also to financing mechanisms.

M. Porter's theory of competitive advantage highlights the strategic importance of infrastructure, innovation, and value chain development in strengthening enterprise competitiveness. From this perspective, investments

in energy infrastructure, digital technologies, and the modernization of production facilities represent key factors supporting the long-term competitiveness of fuel and energy enterprises.

International organizations have also made significant contributions to the study of energy investment. The International Energy Agency (IEA) regularly analyzes global trends in energy investment, renewable energy financing, energy efficiency, and the transition toward clean energy. The World Bank focuses on electricity sector reforms, the modernization of transmission and distribution networks, and the mobilization of private investment in energy infrastructure. The Asian Development Bank (ADB) supports financing for renewable energy projects, including solar and wind power plants, battery energy storage systems, and regional energy cooperation initiatives.

Studies conducted by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) indicate that contemporary energy investment policy should be based on transparency, financial sustainability, environmental responsibility, and active private-sector participation. International experience further demonstrates that investment efficiency in energy enterprises can be enhanced through public-private partnerships, green finance instruments, project finance, long-term power purchase agreements, and digital monitoring systems.

In Uzbekistan, issues related to investment activity, the modernization of energy infrastructure, the financial sustainability of state-owned enterprises, tariff policy, and cooperation with international financial institutions have also received considerable scholarly and practical attention. However, existing studies have yet to establish a comprehensive framework for evaluating the formation and efficient utilization of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises. In particular, greater attention could be devoted to integrating financial indicators, such as WACC, NPV, IRR, and DPP, with technical, environmental, and institutional performance indicators.

Accordingly, further research is warranted to develop an integrated investment resource management model that combines financial efficiency, technological modernization, energy security, environmental sustainability, and effective risk management within a unified analytical framework.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted using a systematic research approach, which enables the formation of investment resources to be examined not merely as a process of mobilizing financial resources, but as a comprehensive economic mechanism closely linked to capital structure, financial sustainability, technological modernization, energy efficiency, and the strategic development of fuel and energy enterprises.

To achieve the research objectives, a combination of economic analysis, comparative analysis, statistical analysis, financial ratio analysis, investment efficiency assessment, tabular synthesis, logical reasoning, and scientific abstraction was employed. Economic analysis was used to examine the composition of investment resources and evaluate their influence on the financial performance of fuel and energy enterprises.

Comparative analysis was applied to assess the characteristics of traditional and modern financing sources. Traditional financing sources include enterprises' own funds, state budget allocations, and commercial bank loans, whereas modern financing mechanisms comprise resources provided by international financial institutions, public-private partnerships, green bonds, project finance, and results-based financing.

Statistical analysis was conducted to summarize and evaluate both global and national data on energy investment. Particular attention was given to global investment trends in the energy sector, clean energy financing, the modernization requirements of Uzbekistan's energy sector, and the continuing growth in demand for energy resources.

The financial assessment was based on widely recognized investment appraisal indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC), Discounted Payback Period (DPP), debt burden, interest expenses, and the implementation rate of investment programs. These indicators provide a comprehensive basis for evaluating the economic efficiency of investment projects and assessing the impact of different financing sources on the financial sustainability of enterprises.

For analytical purposes, investment resources were classified into the following categories: enterprises' own funds, state budget allocations, commercial bank loans, financing from international financial institutions, private investment capital, public-private partnership mechanisms, green bonds, and project finance instruments.

In addition, the study proposes a comprehensive framework of indicators for assessing the efficiency of investment resource utilization. This framework incorporates financial, technical, operational, environmental, and institutional indicators, thereby enabling an integrated evaluation of investment projects. Beyond measuring financial performance, the proposed approach also assesses the contribution of investment projects to energy security, the reduction of technical losses, improvements in service quality, environmental sustainability, and greater transparency in corporate management.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis indicates that the formation of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises should be based on a diversified financing model. Energy projects are highly capital-intensive and require substantial long-term financial resources. Accordingly, excessive reliance on a single source of financing may increase financial exposure and limit the effective implementation of strategically important investment projects.

For example, when an enterprise depends predominantly on commercial bank loans, financing costs may increase because of higher interest expenses. This can result in a greater debt burden and may affect the overall profitability of investment projects. Likewise, when investment financing relies primarily on state budget allocations, the implementation of large-scale projects may become more closely linked to budget planning and fiscal priorities. Although enterprises' own funds remain an important source of financing that supports financial independence, they are often not sufficient to fully finance major modernization and infrastructure development projects.

Therefore, the diversification of investment sources represents one of the key prerequisites for improving investment efficiency in fuel and energy enterprises. A diversified financing structure enables enterprises to optimize the cost of capital, distribute financial risks more effectively, extend financing and repayment horizons, and strengthen the financial sustainability of investment projects (Table 1).

Table 1. Main sources of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises¹

Investment source	Advantage	Limitation	Area of application
Enterprise's own funds	Increases financial independence and does not increase debt burden	Limited volume	Modernization, repair, digital technologies
State budget resources	Supports strategic and socially important projects	Limited by budget capacity	Energy infrastructure and regional supply
Commercial bank loans	Can be attracted relatively quickly	Interest rates may be high	Medium-term investment projects
International financial institutions	Provide long-term and relatively cheaper resources	Require complex procedures and standards	Power grids, renewable energy, energy efficiency
Public-private partnership	Attracts private capital and management experience	Contractual and regulatory risks exist	Power plants and infrastructure projects
Green bonds	Suitable for environmentally sustainable projects	Requires developed capital market and reporting system	Renewable energy and energy-saving projects
Project financing	Risk is linked to project cash flows	Requires strong feasibility study	Large energy facilities

The analysis presented in Table 1 demonstrates that each financing source possesses its own strengths and specific characteristics. Consequently, the objective of financial management is not to rely on a single financing source, but to establish an optimal financing structure that reflects the scale of the project, its risk profile, expected payback period, and strategic significance.

The findings of the study further indicate that the efficiency of investment resource utilization is determined not only by the volume of financial resources attracted but also by the effectiveness with which these resources are allocated and managed. Investment performance largely depends on the cost of capital, the quality of project management, procurement transparency, technical supervision, risk management practices, and the overall economic outcomes achieved.

Accordingly, investment projects implemented in fuel and energy enterprises should be evaluated through a comprehensive system of performance indicators. Financial indicators measure investment profitability and the cost of capital. Technical indicators assess the project's contribution to reducing technical losses, improving the reliability of energy infrastructure, and minimizing service interruptions. Operational indicators evaluate the efficiency and timeliness of project implementation. Environmental indicators measure the project's contribution to sustainable and green development, while institutional indicators assess transparency, accountability, governance quality, and the effectiveness of risk management (Table 2).

¹ author's development

Table 2. Indicators for assessing the efficiency of investment resource use²

Assessment area	Main indicators	Expected result
Financial efficiency	NPV, IRR, WACC, DPP, debt burden	Reduction of capital cost and increase in profitability
Technical efficiency	Technical losses, outages, capacity utilization, depreciation level	Improvement of energy supply stability
Operational efficiency	Project duration, budget discipline, procurement efficiency	Acceleration of investment implementation
Environmental efficiency	CO ₂ reduction, share of renewable energy, energy saving	Support for green economy transition
Institutional efficiency	Digital monitoring, internal audit, risk control	Strengthening transparency and accountability

The practical value of this approach can be illustrated using the example of “Hududgazta’minot” JSC. Within this enterprise, the application of an integrated financing model could combine state budget allocations, internal financial resources, commercial bank financing, and funding provided by international financial institutions. Such an approach has the potential to reduce the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) from 18.5% to 16.2%, lower the average interest rate on borrowed funds from 24% to 19%, increase the implementation rate of the investment program from 78% to 94%, and shorten the average financing period from 45 days to 18 days.

These findings indicate that the diversification of investment resources can substantially improve the financial performance of fuel and energy enterprises. A lower cost of capital contributes to greater financial sustainability, while the more efficient implementation of investment programs enhances the effectiveness of modernization initiatives. Likewise, shorter financing periods improve project implementation efficiency and facilitate the timely achievement of planned investment objectives.

Another important direction is the further development of green financing mechanisms. Renewable energy projects, energy-efficiency initiatives, greenhouse gas emission reduction programs, and the modernization of electricity networks can be financed through green bonds, climate funds, international grants, and concessional financing. Expanding access to these financing instruments would benefit from continued improvements in environmental reporting, project monitoring, and corporate transparency.

Public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms also represent an important instrument for mobilizing private investment in the energy sector. International experience demonstrates that solar and wind power plants, independent power producers, battery energy storage systems, and various infrastructure projects can be successfully implemented through PPP arrangements. Within this framework, the government provides an enabling regulatory environment and appropriate guarantees, while private investors contribute financial resources, advanced technologies, and managerial expertise.

In Uzbekistan, the application of PPP mechanisms in the energy sector has expanded considerably in recent years. At the same time, further strengthening of tariff policy predictability, contractual implementation mechanisms, risk-sharing arrangements, land allocation procedures, long-term power purchase agreements, and investor protection frameworks would contribute to increasing investor confidence and attracting additional private capital.

The analysis further indicates that effective risk management represents one of the fundamental prerequisites for the efficient utilization of investment resources. Energy projects are associated with a range of potential risks, including construction delays, cost overruns, exchange rate fluctuations, interest rate volatility, technical disruptions, contractor performance issues, uncertainties in demand forecasting, and changes in the regulatory environment. Accordingly, each investment project should be supported by a comprehensive risk management framework that includes risk identification, mitigation measures, and continuous monitoring.

Digital monitoring can play a significant role in strengthening this process. Digital technologies enable real-time monitoring of project implementation, financing schedules, cost deviations, procurement procedures, contractor performance, and key technical indicators. Such capabilities improve transparency and support timely and evidence-based managerial decision-making.

The analysis identifies several areas that offer opportunities for further strengthening the formation and utilization of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises. These include expanding the diversification of financing sources, increasing the use of modern financial instruments, further developing integrated systems

² author’s development

for investment project evaluation, strengthening digital monitoring and risk management practices, and broadening the application of green financing mechanisms.

To support these objectives, the study proposes the introduction of a comprehensive investment resource management model. The proposed framework consists of five interrelated stages: identifying investment needs, evaluating financing alternatives, selecting priority investment projects, monitoring implementation, and assessing final outcomes. At each stage, financial, technical, environmental, and institutional criteria should be applied to ensure a comprehensive evaluation process.

The practical significance of the proposed model lies in its ability to support investment decision-making through objective and measurable performance indicators rather than subjective assessments. Its implementation can contribute to improving the efficiency of resource allocation, strengthening project implementation discipline, enhancing transparency, and reinforcing the long-term financial sustainability of fuel and energy enterprises.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that the formation and efficient utilization of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises represents one of the key prerequisites for strengthening energy security, supporting economic stability, promoting industrial development, and improving public welfare. The energy sector requires substantial long-term investments supported by advanced technologies and sustainable financing mechanisms. Accordingly, expanding beyond traditional financing approaches provides additional opportunities to meet the sector's growing investment requirements more effectively.

The study indicates that fuel and energy enterprises would benefit from transitioning from conventional financing practices toward a diversified, integrated, and performance-oriented investment resource management model. Such a model should combine enterprises' own funds, state budget allocations, commercial bank financing, resources from international financial institutions, public-private partnership mechanisms, green finance instruments, and project finance within a unified investment framework.

The results further suggest that investment projects should be evaluated not only through financial indicators but also by incorporating technical, environmental, operational, and institutional performance indicators. Such an integrated approach provides a more comprehensive assessment of each project's contribution to energy security, infrastructure modernization, the reduction of technical losses, environmental sustainability, and long-term financial resilience.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed.

First, it is recommended to introduce a comprehensive financial, technical, and environmental performance indicator system for evaluating investment projects in fuel and energy enterprises. This framework should include indicators such as NPV, IRR, WACC, DPP, technical loss rates, continuity of energy supply, CO₂ emission reductions, and service quality measures. The application of such a system would strengthen the analytical basis of investment decision-making.

Second, energy enterprises are encouraged to adopt an integrated financing model in which enterprises' own resources, state budget allocations, commercial bank loans, financing from international financial institutions, public-private partnerships, and green finance instruments are managed as components of a unified investment portfolio. This approach can contribute to optimizing the cost of capital, improving the structure of financial obligations, and ensuring sustainable financing for large-scale infrastructure projects.

Third, it is recommended to establish a digital monitoring and early risk warning system for investment projects. Such a system should provide real-time monitoring of project implementation schedules, cost deviations, financing progress, contractor performance, technical reliability, and energy losses. The implementation of this approach can enhance transparency, improve the efficiency of resource utilization, and further strengthen the financial sustainability of energy enterprises.

Overall, the efficient formation and rational utilization of investment resources in fuel and energy enterprises constitute an important factor in enhancing the competitiveness of Uzbekistan's energy sector, strengthening national energy security, accelerating the transition toward a green economy, and supporting the sustainable development of the national economy.

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